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Introduction to Organizational Development and Changes

ABSTRACT

This study simply explain the reason of taking the module organizational development and changes, and student's perspective on future career by UBD student particularly. The am of this research is to identify how the organizational and national culture shape your perspective on future career.

INTRODUCTION

The main reason for taking the module BB-4312, Organizational Development and Changes is having this as one of my major option and specific interest in this module as it mainly focus on development and changes of company and organization. However, as I was going through the module selection as I need the minimum module of 6 for this semester, this module title attract my attention fully rather than other module.

As every student can admit, UBD has taught lots of new things and made changes such that teamwork or team project makes a good communication way towards other people or student. This simply means that UBD has improve social skills as it is very useful for student in the future career and job interview. Team's enables people to cooperate, enhance individual skills and provide constructive feedback with out any conflict between individuals (Jones et al., 2007). Moreover, as UBD's most tutorial classes introduce presentation in every week, this may enhance student's bravery to make action such as asking questions, correcting a mistake and to start an argument or debate. Other than that, as UBD's assignment are given deadlines for submission, this practice student to treat punctuality as one of their important ethics.

Furthermore , since UBD'S lecturer mostly told students to do research about the lecture before it was to be introduce the for next lecture classes. In this way, student tend to feel patience, independent and may improve a good practice in becoming a good researcher in which may help in their career life in the future. On the other hand, UBD provide a low allowance for the students such that it was only enough for food and fuel, not saving onto their account, this reminded the students that in their future career that if they have enough salary, they could save it more better than what the allowance had given. Moreover, student who studied in UBD may also enhance performance in-terms of decision making, respect towards elderly, and leadership as these practices were mostly used during lectures and tutorials. Lastly, time management may also be improved as timetable arrangement are self-made and self-registration onto the module preferred as well as examination and tutorial classes

References

Jones, A., Richard, B., Paul, D., Sloane K., and Peter, F. (2007). Effectiveness of teambuilding in organization. *Journal of Management*, 5(3), 35-37.